

FACTORS AND TOOLS FOR INCLUDING MODERN COMPETENCIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

Munavvarkhanova Mahliyokhan Muzaffarkhan kizi

Student of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6553257>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th May 2022

Accepted: 10th May 2022

Online: 15th May 2022

KEY WORDS

Knowledge, competencies,
“National Training
Program”, education
system, basic
competencies.

ABSTRACT

This article describes the knowledge, competencies, additions to the education system, the views of writers on knowledge, as well as the views of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The greatest wealth is intelligence, the greatest inheritance is education, the greatest poverty is ignorance.

Sh.M.Mirziyoyev

Knowledge is the actual information that people create about social events and how they are reflected in human thinking. Such belief is knowledge if we believe in what is in our daily imagination and this belief does not contradict the events and happenings (events) we are accustomed to.

Today, a lot of attention is paid to the education system in our country. With this in mind, it is really important to educate and bring up a patriotic, educated, intelligent and harmoniously developed generation that meets modern requirements. The reason is that the same system of education in the educational process leads to the fact that the recipient is not only educated, but also educated and well-mannered. With this in mind, under

the leadership of President Islam Karimov, measures are being developed to further improve the quality of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Much has been done today to update and improve the content of education, increase the effectiveness of teaching and professionalism of teachers, and disseminate best pedagogical practices. From the first years of independence, the state's main tasks have been to reform the education system, improve new SST and curricula, and create new textbooks. The National Training Program provided the legal basis for this. While the previous curricula and laws were sufficient for students to meet the above-mentioned DTS requirements, the concept of “Competence” was introduced in the newly developed curricula. It sets a number of requirements not only for the knowledge of students, but also for the knowledge, skills and abilities of teachers.

Competence is the ability to apply theoretical knowledge, practical skills and abilities in science to solve practical and theoretical problems encountered in everyday life. Competency-based education is the education of students to develop the competencies to apply the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in their personal, professional and social activities. Basic competencies are developed accordingly:

- Communicative competence;
- Competence in working with information;
- Competence for personal development;
- Socially active civic competence;
- General cultural competence;
- Competence in mathematical literacy, knowledge and use of scientific and technical innovations.

Well-known Russian writer AP Chekhov said: "Our job is to read and study, to strive for as much knowledge as

possible, because serious social trends - where there is knowledge, the future happiness of mankind is only in knowledge. We need smart, knowledgeable people; as humanity approaches a brighter life, their numbers will continue to grow until they make up the majority. Everyone should be able to see and know more than their fathers and grandfathers saw and knew" he said. Indeed, not only Chekhov, but thousands of writers, scientists and scholars, in their biographies and in many of their works, have argued that knowledge is a powerful force, that it is capable of anything, and that ignorance is the most vulnerable, even ruining human life. mentioned.

From all of the above, it can be concluded that part of a person's life is spent on learning, and the rest is spent on applying this knowledge in life. We need to understand that the knowledge acquired by our people in their youth is like a pattern carved in stone.

References:

1. "Pedagogy" (R. Mavlonova, O. Turaeva, K. Kholikberdiyev). Tashkent "Teacher" 2001. Pages 462-463.
2. "Pedagogy" (R. Mavlonova, O. Turaeva, K. Kholikberdiyev). Tashkent "Teacher" 2001. Pages 465-466.
3. K. Hoshimov and others - "History of Pedagogy" - Tashkent, Teacher, 1996.